

EMERGENCE OF YOUTUBE AS KEY EDUCATION PLATFORM IN THE PANDEMIC: EFFECTIVE, ECONOMICAL AND ENTERTAINING

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Abstract :

India has the highest population belonging to the teenage group who are by default techno savvy. Being the generation zee; they are well versed with the social media and the content streaming on web portals. Parents have dual task now; to moderate the content on screen time of the children but also provide the infrastructure to learn on digital platform. Cell phone is now the essential evil. The constant screen time impacts on the cognitive and psychological growth of the child. All the virtual games make the kids lazy and believe that all outdoor games could be played through the computers; sitting in air conditioned houses without a drop of sweat. This is equally dangerous preposition to the healthy lifestyle of the teenagers. As of toddlers, they won't have their meal till the parents turn on the cartoons on the YouTube. YouTube is highly addictive!

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Introduction :

YouTube is not just any normal application; it has grip over the screen time of all the people from the age group of 3 to 90 years old people. Initially started as a platform to upload, share and view videos - it has become India's largest education platform. The free of cost viewing of several tutorial, lectures, blogs etc. has made it a popular front as educational hub. Of a study conducted by several data analysts; it was observed that YouTube has a screen time of almost 4 Billion Man hours each month across the globe; with each minute adding a content of more than 90 hours. Several of key players in the education industry are using YouTube as a launch pad to start their career of online educators. The economical and easily accessible content on the click makes it the most prominent platform in Digital India.

India has the highest population belonging to the teenage group who are by default techno savvy. Being the generation zee; they are well versed with the social media and the content streaming on web portals. Parents have dual task now; to moderate the content on screen time of the children but also provide the infrastructure to learn on digital platform. Cell phone is now the essential evil. The constant screen time impacts on the cognitive and psychological growth of the child. All the virtual games make the kids lazy and believe that all outdoor games could be played

through the computers; sitting in air conditioned houses without a drop of sweat. This is equally dangerous proposition to the healthy lifestyle of the teenagers. As of toddlers, they won't have their meal till the parents turn on the cartoons on the YouTube. YouTube is highly addictive!

Objectives :

1. What are the issues faced by Indian students while taking education from Online Platform?
2. Is the free and open source like YouTube reliable for educational or research purpose?

Literature Review :

1. In the paper by Alias, Norlidah & Razak, Siti & elHadad, Ghada & Kunjambu, Nurul & Muniandy, Parimaladevi (2013) it was mentioned about the content analysis and cross analysis, insights etc. about research trends on YouTube were studied in depth by the author. They also provided various insights that the viewers pursued before using the application.
2. Mullen and Wedwick (2008) in their paper suggested that the in the new digital era of education, digital classroom teaching would play in important role in upcoming years especially with the GenZee era.
3. As per Yu & Smith (2008) technology had reached to the optimum heights that it could be utilized for more interactive conversation with students and teachers who are separated by geographical barriers. A person in the most isolated part of the world can learn; all he needs to have is a stable internet connection. Interactive media also improves the student's retention strength and encourages him to study longer with interest.
4. As per Juhasz (2008) presently the cyber space is being rushed with all junk from all the parts of the globe. The content is highly plagiarized and needs to be monitored strictly for any infringement of copyright. The accuracy of the data is also to be validated. Genuine content should be promoted while cyber dust should be trashed.
5. Mullen and Wedwick (2008) stated that YouTube promotes all types of genre; but there should be strict policy to filter for age group below 9, 12, 15 and 18 respectively. Parental controls are mandatory for such free circulated uncensored media. If possible, the appropriate censor board should be established for effective monitoring.

Brief Introduction of YouTube :

In 2005, YouTube was started just as a startup for the sharing of videos on online platform with no intention to convert it to any education purpose. The founders were clear about the audience and the utility it might provide - free sharing of cloud space and videos across global network. Initially the founders were not of the opinion to monetize the stream links by advertisement. It was however 10 years later that the startup started to give pop up advertisement and 15 years later that it started a premium package of ad free content. 15 years' time they were not charging any money to the users. Data privacy and content were highly controversial topic of Privacy. But the 99% users were not having issue with the YouTube data policy; the 1% were engaged in the long drawn legal battle with no ending.

Features that make YouTube Unique :

1. Limitless space
2. Global coverage
3. Anonymity
4. Interactive
5. 24 / 7 service
6. Affordable and Economical
7. Minimum compliance requirement

Limitations to YouTube for Education Purpose :

1. No censorship
2. Content is not authenticated or verified
3. No qualification required to be educator
4. Highly sensitive and controversial topics could be cause of

Key Highlights of YouTube :

Children's basic education format has changed to a large extent in the surge of Covid - 19 pandemic. Digital footprints across all the electronic devices are capturing our attention. The enforced digital transformation on the young generation which was enjoying to start with is becoming monotonous and lacking motivation. It opened doors for various initiatives like blogging and research; yet it is kept to be properly compartmentalized. The genre are being misplaced; using '#' Hashtags you can gain the clicks of disinterested viewers also - surrogate advertisements. The frustration caused by various unessential videos also infuriates the viewers. Children adapted well to the online platforms of learning and YouTube really nicely. It was the teachers who faced the pain and efforts of upskilling themselves with the task of learning the evolving education culture. The barrier was too huge to climb in limited time. Technology has polarized the senses to making all answers available at just one click. The social media as a platform for skill set development and also entertainment could be used simultaneously. The infotainment has placed before us the new phenomenon of meaningful social interactivity. Development for the sake of development should be prohibited. Unless something meaningful arises out of it, we should not be too critical and negative about the approach. Pandemic has forced us to teach online, but not this is the new era of education - we must adapt and adopt.

The user should make an informed decision with regards to the content to be viewed on the streaming platforms like YouTube. It need not require any programming or advanced IT skills, but basic creativity is required to make the optimum use of the social media platforms. It gives the younger generation upper hand in the advanced technical superiority over their aged peers. YouTube comments are also interactive which allows the viewers to give instant feedback on the educator.

For special education purpose or for technical or practical oriented courses the YouTube is a disastrous idea. Special children require attention which the recorded videos cannot partake. Learn on own efforts is not applicable

to them. They require a counsellor, mentor or a teacher who holds their hands and can act like a friend to them. YouTube does not have this personal touch. As for the practical subjects; you cannot learn surgery online. It's not like baking a cake or preparing a dish after watching the process online. YouTube has facilitated many hobbies or vocational trainings; but it cannot compete with the experience of a trained experienced doctor to teach medical students.

Those users who were using WhatsApp groups as means of official communication prior to lockdown or using google classroom to collect assignments are not facing must issue to the digital transition. They were well versed with online cloud space phenomenon; but the challenge occurred when you have to present the lecture in front of blank screen. Lecture delivery in front of a blank audience is the torturous punishment to any teacher; but assume the punishment inflicted on the teacher for over two years. Many have left the jobs as lecturers due to this mental trauma. In YouTube there is no fixed time for the lecture schedule, the teacher uploads the video a day prior & the students can view the same at their own pace. The benefit of this mode of learning is that - at own pace also they can watch the lecture series over a numerous times till they are satisfied with the understanding.

The drawback of YouTube is that several formalities of the Google Policies have to be completed prior to the uploading of the videos, YouTube live is not allowed unless you comply with those mandates. There is a limit to the number of time the video could be uploaded, streamed or live interaction taking place. The lecture limits again to one hours of maximum stream per video or per day. Hence it is not suitable for courses which require long hours of uninterrupted practical training. YouTube has also started to monetize their content; hence unwanted advertisement pop ups come at regular intervals to annoy the viewers.

Since the delivery of lectures is saved on cloud space, teachers become conscious of the fact that anyone can watch them at any time and criticize publicly. Also, given a chance to edit, modify or retake the video again and again, the educators opt for perfection and have to redo the same thing over 3 to 4 times before they are satisfied. Oddly so, the first take is their best take - after having redone the same task dozen time; they feel.

Data Analysis :

A. Search as per Applications used.

Source of Users	No. of Users	%
YouTube Search	452680	33
Suggested Link / URLs	264529	19.4
Third Party Links	256245	19
Web Search	229272	17
Facebook	107893	8
Misc.	48552	3.6

Source - Big Data Analysis of a Dedicated YouTube Channel as an Open Educational Resource in Hand Surgery; Norana Abdul Rahman, Hannah Jia Hui Ng and Vaikunthan Rajaratnam

As it could be seen in the above chart, maximum number of user refer to YouTube for their queries and doubt solving, but maximum search are routed through official YouTube website or application. The next max use occurs

with suggested URLs which are then forwarded through from one device to others. Miscellaneous application are also key players in the transfer of content which is previously uploaded on YouTube in form of web links.

B. Use of YouTube for Educational Purpose - Country Wise

Country	% users globally
USA	23.5
Malaysia	18
India	15
UK	12
South Korea	7.8
Japan	6
Others	17.7

Source - Big Data Analysis of a Dedicated YouTube Channel as an Open Educational Resource in Hand Surgery; Norana Abdul Rahman, Hannah Jia Hui Ng and Vaikunthan Rajaratnam

C. Views by Device Type (%)

Device	%
Computer	48
Mobile	22
Tablet	20
Television	8.6
Gaming Console	0.9
Others	0.5

Conclusion :

This data validated that the maximum student's age group prefer YouTube Channels for educational purpose and through multiple devices. The channel is free for all, can be used any time from any place and is running on any of the device. Soon YouTube could be the next education hub catering to students of various gender, race, culture, country, age etc.

References :

1. Alias, Norlidah & Razak, Siti & elHadad, Ghada & Kunjambu, Nurul & Muniandy, Parimaladevi. (2013). A Content Analysis in the Studies of YouTube in Selected Journals. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 103. 10-18. 10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.301.
2. Juhasz, A. (2008), 4 lessons of YouTube for Activists. Conference paper delivered at OurMedia, August 2008, Accra, Ghana.
3. Chang & Huang (2020), antecedents predicting health information seeking: a systematic review and meta-analysis, *IJIM*, 54 (2020), Article 102115
4. Digital inclusion: A review of international policy and practice Digital inclusion: A review of international policy and practice
5. De Souza & Dick (2009), Disclosure of information by children in social networking-Not just a case of "you show me yours and I'll show you mine", *International Journal of Information Management*, 29 (4) (2009), pp. 255-261

Webliography :

- <https://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=EDU/WKP%282019%293&docLanguage=En>

- <https://www.brookings.edu/research/the-opportunities-and-challenges-of-digital-learning/>
- <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1287167.pdf>
- <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590291120300905>
- <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2021.705013/full>
- <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=9683&context=libphilprac>
- <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2347631120983481>
- <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0268401220310264#bibl0005>
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280289182_A_Content_Analysis_in_the_Studies_of_YouTube_in_Selected_Journals

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